

MORE WIDE USE OF SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES OF MODULAR TRAINING

U.A. Qasimov

head of the department "Pedagogy and psychology, educational technologies" of the Bukhara region national center for training pedagogues in new methods,
Ph.D, associate professor

ABSTRACT

The article describes the issues of increasing the effectiveness of advanced training through modular training and the wider use of its capabilities, and makes appropriate conclusions and recommendations.

Key words: modular teaching, module, taxonomy

Effectiveness of modern education, wider use of its opportunities, remains one of the main requirements for the implementation of education.

If we organize the educational process in any way, its implementation mechanism should be compact, understandable, convenient for practical use, if we can choose the most optimal means and methods of independent knowledge improvement and at the same time spend the least amount of time on mastering it. Advanced teachers and Methodist scientists were not indifferent to such things as raising the horse.

As a result of research in this regard, new ideas were put forward; including optimization of education, gradual assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities, activating the listener's activity and turning it into an object of the educational process, programmed education, etc.

One of the currently widespread methods of effective teaching is the "modular system of teaching".

Modul means "standard" in Latin. It is known that the acquired knowledge has the value of certain logically complete, indivisible corresponding quantities. For example: let's take concepts, the thought that arose during the formation of a concept is expressed through speech by turning it into a combination of words. Thus, we see that the concept is the main indivisible structure of knowledge, and this norm of indivisible knowledge is a module. (ie: certain rates, rules, theorems, laws, axioms, etc.)

The modular education system was created based on the learning system, which is a feature of the human brain. The human brain perceives the unit of information best as a stream, not as a whole, but as a quantum (indivisible quantity). Based on this, it is recognized that the most effective way is to organize education, i.e. teaching, based on the idea of adapting the human brain to the learning system.

The micro-module in each module fulfills a certain goal and task in the formation of specialized subjects, its goals are reflected in the state educational standards or requirements and represents the main goal of developing the specialized subject.

The module is considered an independent structural unit, and in training, learners do not need to study the entire course, but can study only a number of modules. It also allows talented students to optimally plan their individual and independent work (modular credit system).

The purpose of switching to modular training is:

- Continuity of education;
- Individualization of education;
- Creating the necessary conditions for independent learning of educational material;
- Acceleration of studies;
- Achieve effective learning of science;
- Achieving full development of listeners' abilities and high teaching results;

- Students are given the opportunity to choose subjects according to their specialty;
- The student will have the opportunity to complete the advanced training program ahead of schedule.

The beginning of modular teaching technology is the definition of teaching objectives of the subject. It is its continuation, and it is in setting educational goals by subject. Theoretical and practical training are educational processes aimed at specific goals. These processes are carried out to achieve specific learning objectives. If learning objectives are not defined, then the content and didactic structure of the lesson will be broken. It is important to develop suitable educational goals in advance for the formation of theoretical and practical training.

It is recommended to use pedagogic taxonomies to classify educational goals into categories and sequence levels, and to clearly structure educational goals. Taxonomy (derived from the Greek word "taxis" meaning arrangement and "homos" meaning law). Taxonomy includes a category based on the natural relationship of objects and a multi-level principle for describing objects. The taxonomy of educational objectives of the American pedagogue B. Bloom is the most widespread taxonomy in the world. In practice, learning objectives are developed for each theoretical and practical lesson. These objectives are classified in the taxonomy under the following headings:

1. Knowing means remembering and recalling facts and principles. In this case, the listener can remember the acquired knowledge and tell them.

2. Comprehension is an indicator of the ability to understand the essence of the studied material, draw conclusions, analyze the current situation. Explaining, summarizing the material or making suggestions about further events, etc. are involved as an indicator of understanding.

3. Application of methods, rules, general concepts - this includes the application of rules, methods, concepts, principles, theories. In this case, learning outcomes require mastering the learning material at a higher level than understanding it.

4. To analyze - to be able to divide the whole into elements, to be able to establish the gradation and relationships of these elements, to know the principles of organizing the whole. In this case, learning outcomes are characterized by their high intellectual level in relation to understanding and application, as it requires knowledge of the content of the learning material and its internal structure.

5. Synthesis - creating a whole from given elements in order to create new structures. Appropriate results represent activities of a creative nature aimed at creating new schemes and structures.

6. Evaluation - evaluation of materials and methods taking into account the adopted goals. This category requires achievement of learning outcomes for all previous categories and evaluative judgments based on clearly defined criteria.

When defining educational goals, the educational goals of the subject are determined using adequate verbs, that is, when expressing the goal, it is necessary to describe it with such a word (verb) that the goal is immediately understandable, therefore, each topic It is necessary to specify the base phrases separately. It will be necessary to establish each base phrase, the depth of study. That is, the listener will have to master some basic phrase at the level of knowledge, use another, and evaluate some basic phrases. An example of verb coordination in the clear classification of educational goals can be shown in the following table:

T.r.	Classification of educational goals	O'quv maqsadlarini toifalashtiruvchi fe'llar	O'quv maqsadlarini toifalashtiruvchi fe'llar muvofiqlanishi
1	Knowing	Say it back Note Notification to name To call to write	Expression Difference Recognition To tell Repeat

2	Understanding	Give evidence to exchange Identify, mark to explain	Transfer, convert Change Show with photo Explaining, revealing
3	Application	Application Calculation Demonstration Use, teach	Determination Execution Calculation Implementation, solution
4	Analysis	Bring out Highlight Differentiation Classification Invitation	To tell in advance compartmentalization Distribution Check Grouping
5	Synthesis	Discovery Generalization Planning Development	Systematization to add, connect Compilation Projecting
6	Evaluation	Diagnose Proof Justification Measure Approval	Evaluation, inspection Controlling Compare and contrast to compare

Thus, the more clearly the learning objectives are expressed and categorized, the easier it is to assess the level of achievement. The more we can correctly categorize and define educational goals, the closer we will be to achieving them.

To sum up, in modular teaching, each specialty subject is considered as a whole module, and the system of subjects studied in it is considered micro-modules of a whole module, and this micro-module is in turn divided into smaller modules, and the listener is this during the passage through the system of modules, he acquires the subject continuously and consistently in connection with other subjects.

REFERENCES

1. Borodina N.V., Samoiloa Ye.S. Modular technology and professional education. Fly away. posobie. Yekaterinburg.- 1998.
2. N.Kh. Avliyokulov N.Kh. Modern teaching technologies. "Author" .- 2001.